

REGULAR SEMIOPEN SOFT SETS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS

E. ELAVARASAN* AND A. VADIVEL

ABSTRACT. The purpose of this paper is to introduce the notion of soft regular semi compactness, connectedness, and separation axioms using regular semiopen soft sets in soft topological spaces. Moreover, we investigate soft RS -regular space and soft RS -normal space are soft topological properties under bijection, soft regular semi irresolute and soft regular semi irresolute open functions. Also, we show that the properties of being soft regular semi T_i -spaces ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are hereditary properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of soft sets was first introduced by Molodtsov [17] in 1999 as a general mathematical tool for dealing with uncertain objects. In [17, 18], Molodtsov successfully applied the soft theory in several directions, such as smoothness of functions, game theory, operations research, Riemann integration, Perron integration, probability, theory of measurement, and so on. After presentation of the operations of soft sets [12], the properties and applications of soft set theory have been studied increasingly [3, 11, 17, 20]. In recent years, many interesting applications of soft set theory have been expanded by embedding the ideas of fuzzy sets [1, 4, 5, 7, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 22, 26]. To develop soft set theory, the operations of the soft sets are redefined and a uni-int decision making method was constructed by using these new operations [8]. Recently, in 2011, Shabir and Naz [23] initiated the study of soft topological spaces. They defined basic notions of soft topological spaces such as open soft and closed soft sets, soft subspace, soft closure, soft nbd of a point, soft separation axioms, soft regular spaces and soft normal spaces and established their several properties. Min in [16] investigate some properties of these soft separation axioms mentioned in [23]. Banu and Halis in [6] studied some properties of soft Hausdorff space. Recently Vadivel and Elavarasan [24] introduced the concept of regular semiopen soft set.

The main purpose of this paper is to introduce the notion of soft regular semi compactness, connectedness, and separation axioms using regular semiopen soft sets in soft topological spaces. In particular we study the properties of the soft RS -regular spaces and soft RS -normal spaces. We show that if (x, E) is regular semiclosed soft set for all

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*Corresponding author.

$x \in X$ in a soft topological space (X, τ, E) , then (X, τ, E) is soft regular semi T_1 -space. Also, we show that if a soft topological space (X, τ, E) is soft regular semi T_3 -space, then $\forall x \in X, (x, E)$ is regular semiclosed soft set. This paper, not only can form the theoretical basis for further applications of topology on soft sets, but also lead to the development of information systems.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we recall some definition and concepts discussed in [9, 16, 23, 25]. Throughout this study X and Y denote universal sets, E, E' denote two sets of parameters, $A, B, C, D, B', D' \subseteq E$ or E' . Let X be an initial universe and E be a set of parameters. Let $\mathbb{P}(X)$ denote the power set of X and A be a nonempty subset set of E . A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over X , where F is a mapping given by $F : A \rightarrow \mathbb{P}(X)$. For two soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over common universe X , we say that (F, A) is a soft subset (G, B) if $A \subseteq B$ and $F(e) \subseteq G(e)$, for all $e \in A$. In this case, we write $(F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, B)$ and (G, B) is said to be a soft super set of (F, A) . Two soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over a common universe X are said to be soft equal if $(F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, B)$ and $(G, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} (F, A)$. The soft set (F, A) over X such that $F(e) = \{x\} \forall e \in E$ is called singleton soft point and denoted by x_E or (x, E) . A soft set (F, A) over X is called null soft set, denoted by (Φ, A) , if for each $e \in A, F(e) = \Phi$. Similarly, it is called absolute soft set, denoted by \widetilde{X} , if for each $e \in A, F(e) = X$.

The union of two soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over the common universe X is the soft set (H, C) , where $C = A \cup B$ and for each $e \in C$,

$$H(e) = \begin{cases} F(e) & e \in A - B \\ G(e) & e \in B - A \\ F(e) \cup G(e) & e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

We write $(F, A) \cup (G, B) = (H, C)$. Moreover, the intersection (H, C) of two soft sets (F, A) and (G, B) over a common universe X , denoted by $(F, A) \cap (G, B)$, is defined as $C = A \cap B$ and $H(e) = F(e) \cap G(e)$ for each $e \in C$. The difference (H, E) of two soft sets (F, E) and (G, E) over X , denoted by $(F, E) - (G, E)$, is defined as $H(e) = F(e) - G(e)$, for each $e \in E$. Let Y be nonempty subset of X . Then \widetilde{Y} denotes the soft set (Y, E) over X where $Y(e) = Y$ for each $e \in E$. In particular, (X, E) will be denoted by \widetilde{X} . Let (F, E) be a soft set over X and $x \in X$. We say that $x \in (F, E)$, whenever $x \in F(e)$, for each $e \in E$ [21].

The relative complement of a soft set (F, A) is denoted by $(F, A)'$ and is defined by $(F, A)' = (F, A)$ where $F' : A \rightarrow \mathbb{P}(X)$ is defined by following

$$F'(e) = X - F(e), \forall e \in A$$

In this paper, for convenience, let $SS(X, E)$ be the family of soft sets over X with set of parameters E . We will apply two next propositions so much in the proofs.

Proposition 2.1. [21] *Let $(F, E), (G, E), (H, E)$ and (I, E) be soft sets (X, E) . Then the following holds:*

- (i) $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, E)$ if and only if $(F, E) \cap (G, E) = (F, E)$;
- (ii) $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, E), (H, E)$ if and only if $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, E) \cap (H, E)$;
- (iii) If $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, E)$ and $(G, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (I, E)$, then $(F, E) \cup (G, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, E) \cup (I, E)$;
- (iv) $(F, E) \cap (F, E)' = (\Phi, E)$;
- (v) $(F, E) \cap (G, E) = (\Phi, E)$ if and only if $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, E)'$;

(vi) $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, E)$ if and only if $(G, E)' \widetilde{\subseteq} (F, E)'$.

Also we can obtain the following easily.

Proposition 2.2. [21] Let (F, E) , (G, E) and (H, E) be soft sets and $\{(F_i, E) | i \in I\}$ be a family of soft sets in (X, E) . Then the following holds.

- (i) $(F, E) \cap (F, E)' = (\Phi, E)$;
- (ii) $(F, E) \cup (\Phi, E) = (F, E)$;
- (iii) $(F, E) \cap (\bigcup_{i \in I} (F_i, E)) = \bigcup_{i \in I} ((F, E) \cap (F_i, E))$;
- (iv) If $(F, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, E)$ and $(G, E) \cap (H, E) = (\Phi, E)$, then $(F, E) \cap (H, E) = (\Phi, E)$;
- (v) $(\Phi, E)' = \widetilde{X}$;
- (vi) $\widetilde{X}' = (\Phi, E)$.

Let τ be the collection of soft sets over X . Then τ is called a soft topology [23] on X if τ satisfies the following axioms:

- (i) (Φ, E) and \widetilde{X} belongs to τ .
- (ii) The union of any number of soft sets in τ belongs to τ .
- (iii) The intersection of any two soft sets in τ belongs to τ .

The triple (X, τ, E) is called soft topological space (briefly, sts) over X . The members of τ are said to be soft open in X , and the soft set (F, E) is called soft closed in X if its relative complement $(F, E)'$ belongs to τ . Let (X, τ, E) be a soft topological space and (F, A) be a soft set over X . Soft closure of a soft set (F, A) in X is denoted by $cl(F, A) = \bigcap \{(F, E) \widetilde{\supseteq} (F, A) : (F, E) \text{ is a soft closed set of } X\}$. Soft interior of a soft set (F, A) in X is denoted by $int(F, A) = \bigcup \{(O, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (F, A) : (O, A) \text{ is a soft open set of } X\}$.

The proof of the following proposition is an easy application of De Morgan's laws with the definition of a soft topology on X (see Proposition 3.3 of [25]).

Proposition 2.3. Let (X, τ, E) be a soft space over X . Then

- (i) (Φ, E) and \widetilde{X} are closed soft sets over X .
- (ii) The intersection of any number of soft closed sets is a soft closed set over X .
- (iii) The union of any two soft closed sets is a soft closed set over X .

Theorem 2.4. [23] Let (Y, τ_Y, E) be a soft subspace of a sts (X, τ, E) and $(F, E) \in SS(X, E)$. Then

- (1) If (F, E) is open soft set in Y and $\widetilde{Y} \in \tau$, then $(F, E) \in \tau$.
- (2) (F, E) is open soft set in Y if and only if $(F, E) = \widetilde{Y} \widetilde{\cap} (G, E)$ for some $(G, E) \in \tau$.
- (3) (F, E) is closed soft set in Y if and only if $(F, E) = \widetilde{Y} \widetilde{\cap} (H, E)$ for some (H, E) is τ -closed soft set.

Definition 2.1. [2] Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and $(F, E) \in SS(X, E)$. Then (F, E) is called a (i) regular closed soft set if $(F, E) = cl(int(F, E))$ and (ii) regular open soft set if $(F, E) = int(cl(F, E))$.

Definition 2.2. [24] In a sts (X, τ, E) , a soft set

- (1) (G, C) is said to be regular semiopen soft (briefly, *RSO* soft) set if \exists an regular open soft set (H, B) such that $(H, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} cl(H, B)$.
- (2) (L, A) is said to be regular semiclosed soft (briefly, *RSC* soft) set if \exists an regular closed soft set (K, D) such that $int(K, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} (L, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (K, D)$.

We shall denote the family of all regular semiopen soft sets (regular semiclosed soft sets) of a sts (X, τ, E) by $RSOSS(X, E)$, $(RSCSS(X, E))$.

Definition 2.3. [24] Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and (G, C) be a soft set over X . Then

- (1) the soft regular semiclosure of (G, C) , $rsscl(G, C) = \widetilde{\bigcap}\{(S, F)|(G, C) \subseteq (S, F) \text{ and } (S, F) \in RSCSS(X, E)\}$ is a soft set.
- (2) the soft regular semiinterior of (G, C) , $rssint(G, C) = \widetilde{\bigcup}\{(S, F)|(S, F) \subseteq (G, C) \text{ and } (S, F) \in RSOSS(X, E)\}$ is a soft set.

Thus $rsscl(G, C)$ is the smallest rscs set containing (G, C) and $rssint(G, C)$ is the largest RSO soft set contained in (G, C) .

Theorem 2.5. [10] Let $SS(X, A)$ and $SS(Y, B)$ be families of soft sets. For the soft function $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$, the following statements hold,

- (a) $f_{pu}^{-1}((G, B)') = (f_{pu}^{-1}(G, B))' \forall (G, B) \in SS(Y, B)$.
- (b) $f_{pu}(f_{pu}^{-1}((G, B))) \subseteq (G, B) \forall (G, B) \in SS(Y, B)$. If f_{pu} is surjective, then the equality holds.
- (c) $(F, A) \subseteq f_{pu}^{-1}(f_{pu}((F, A))) \forall (F, A) \in SS(X, A)$. If f_{pu} is injective, then the equality holds.
- (d) $f_{pu}(\widetilde{X}) \subseteq \widetilde{Y}$. If f_{pu} is surjective, then the equality holds.
- (e) $f_{pu}^{-1}(\widetilde{Y}) = \widetilde{X}$ and $f_{pu}(\Phi, A) = (\Phi, B)$.
- (f) If $(F, A) \subseteq (G, A)$, then $f_{pu}(F, A) \subseteq f_{pu}(G, A)$.
- (g) If $(F, B) \subseteq (G, B)$, then $f_{pu}^{-1}(F, B) \subseteq f_{pu}^{-1}(G, B) \forall (F, B), (G, B) \in SS(Y, B)$.
- (h) $f_{pu}^{-1}[(F, B) \widetilde{\cup} (G, B)] = f_{pu}^{-1}(F, B) \widetilde{\cup} f_{pu}^{-1}(G, B)$ and $f_{pu}^{-1}[(F, B) \widetilde{\cap} (G, B)] = f_{pu}^{-1}(F, B) \widetilde{\cap} f_{pu}^{-1}(G, B) \forall (F, B), (G, B) \in SS(Y, B)$.
- (i) $f_{pu}[(F, A) \widetilde{\cup} (G, A)] = f_{pu}(F, A) \widetilde{\cup} f_{pu}(G, A)$ and $f_{pu}[(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} (G, A)] \subseteq f_{pu}(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} f_{pu}(G, A) \forall (F, A), (G, A) \in SS(X, A)$. If f_{pu} is injective, then the equality holds.

Definition 2.4. [24] Let (X, τ, E) and (Y, τ', E') be two sts's. A soft function $f : SS(X, E) \rightarrow SS(Y, E')$ is said to be

- (i) Soft regular semi continuous (briefly, *SRS*-continuous) if for each open soft set (G, C) of (Y, E') , the inverse image $f^{-1}(G, C)$ is a RSO soft set of (X, E) .
- (ii) Soft regular semi irresolute (briefly, *SRS*-irresolute) if for each RSO soft set (G, C) of (Y, E') , the inverse image $f^{-1}(G, C)$ is a RSO soft set of (X, E) .
- (ii) Soft regular semi irresolute open (briefly, *SRSI*-open) if for each RSO soft set (G, C) of (X, E) , the image $f(G, C)$ is a RSO soft set of (Y, E') .

3. SOFT REGULAR SEMI COMPACTNESS

The study on compactness (which depends on open sets) for a soft topological space was initiated by Zorlutuna et al. in [25]. This section is devoted to introduce regular semi compactness in sts along with its characterization.

Definition 3.1. A cover of a soft set is said to be a soft RSO -cover if every member of the cover is a RSO soft set.

Definition 3.2. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be soft RS -compact if each soft RSO -cover of (X, E) has a finite subcover.

Remark. Every soft RS -compact soft topological space is also soft semi compact.

Theorem 3.1. *A sts (X, τ, E) is soft RS-compact \Leftrightarrow each family of RSC soft sets in (X, E) with the FIP has a nonempty intersection.*

Proof. Let $\{(L_i, A) | i \in I\}$ be a collection of RSC soft sets with the FIP. If possible, assume $\widetilde{\bigcap}_{i \in I} (L_i, A) = (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcup}_{i \in I} (L_i, A)' = (X, E)$. So, the collection $\{(L_i, A)' | i \in I\}$ forms a soft RSO-cover of (X, E) , which is soft RS-compact. So, \exists a finite subcollection I_0 of I which also covers (X, E) . i.e., $\widetilde{\bigcup}_{i \in I_0} (L_i, A)' = (X, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcap}_{i \in I_0} (L_i, A) = (\Phi, E)$, a contradiction.

For the converse, if possible, let (X, τ, E) be not soft RS-compact. Then \exists a soft RSO-cover $\{(G_i, C) | i \in I\}$ of (X, U) , such that for every finite subcollection I_0 of I we have $\widetilde{\bigcup}_{i \in I_0} (G_i, C) \neq (X, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcap}_{i \in I_0} (G_i, C)' \neq (\Phi, E)$. Hence $\{(G_i, C)' | i \in I\}$ has the FIP. So, by hypothesis $\widetilde{\bigcap}_{i \in I_0} (G_i, C)' \neq (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcup}_{i \in I_0} (G_i, C) \neq (X, E)$ a contradiction. \square

Theorem 3.2. *A sts (X, τ, E) is soft RS-compact iff for every family \mathcal{A} of soft sets with FIP, $\widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{A}} r_{sscl}(G, C) \neq (\Phi, E)$.*

Proof. Let (X, τ, E) be soft RS-compact and if possible, let $\widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{A}} r_{sscl}(G, C) = (\Phi, E)$ for some family \mathcal{A} of soft sets with the FIP. So, $\widetilde{\bigcup}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{A}} (r_{sscl}(G, C))' = (X, E) \Rightarrow \mathcal{B} = \{(r_{sscl}(G, C))' | (G, C) \in \mathcal{A}\}$ is a soft RSO-cover of (X, E) . Then by soft RS-compactness of (X, E) , \exists a finite subcover \mathcal{B}_0 of \mathcal{B} . i.e., $\widetilde{\bigcup}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}_0} (r_{sscl}(G, C))' = (X, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcup}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}_0} (G, C)' = (X, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}_0} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$, a contradiction. Hence $\widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{A}} r_{sscl}(G, C) \neq (\Phi, E)$.

Conversely, we have $\widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{A}} r_{sscl}(G, C) \neq (\Phi, E)$, for every family \mathcal{A} of soft sets with FIP. Assume (X, τ, E) is not soft RS-compact. Then \exists a family \mathcal{B} of RSO soft sets covering X without a finite subcover. So, for every finite subfamily \mathcal{B}_0 of \mathcal{B} we have $\widetilde{\bigcup}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}_0} (G, C) \neq (X, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}_0} (G, C)' \neq (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow \{(G, C)' | (G, C) \in \mathcal{B}_0\}$ is a family of soft sets with FIP. Now $\widetilde{\bigcup}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}} (G, C) = (X, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}} (G, C)' = (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\bigcap}_{(G,C) \in \mathcal{B}} r_{ss}(G, C)' = (\Phi, E)$, a contradiction. \square

Theorem 3.3. *SRS-continuous image of a soft RS-compact space is soft compact.*

Proof. Let $f : SS(X, E) \rightarrow SS(Y, E')$ be a SRS-continuous function where (X, τ, E) is a soft RS-compact sts and (Y, δ, E') is another sts. Take a soft open cover $\{(G_i, C) | i \in I\}$ of $(Y, E') \Rightarrow \{f^{-1}((G_i, C)) | i \in I\}$ forms a soft RSO-cover of $(X, E) \Rightarrow \exists$ a finite subset I_0 of I such that $\{f^{-1}((G_i, C)) | i \in I_0\}$ forms a soft RSO-cover of $(X, E) \Rightarrow \{(G_i, C) | i \in I_0\}$ forms a finite soft open cover of (Y, E') . \square

Theorem 3.4. *Soft RSC subspace of a soft RS-compact sts is soft RS-compact.*

Proof. Let (Y, B) be a soft RSC subspace of a soft RS -compact sts (X, τ, A) and $\{(G_i, C) \mid i \in I\}$ be a soft RSO -cover of (Y, B) . Then the family $\{(G_i, C) \mid i \in I\} \cup ((X, A) - (Y, B))$ is a soft RSO -cover of (X, A) , which has a finite subcover, as (X, A) is soft RS -compact. So, $\{(G_i, C) \mid i \in I\}$ has a finite subfamily to cover (Y, B) . Hence (Y, B) is soft RS -compact. \square

Let (X, τ_1, E) and (X, τ_2, E) be soft topological spaces. If $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$, then τ_2 is soft finer than τ_1 . If $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$ or $\tau_2 \subseteq \tau_1$, then τ_1 is soft comparable with τ_2 . Then, we have the following.

Proposition 3.5. *Let (X, τ_2, E) be a soft RS -compact space and $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$. Then (X, τ_1, E) is soft RS -compact.*

Proof. Let $\{(F_i, E) \mid i \in I\}$ be a soft RSO -cover of \tilde{X} by RSO soft sets of (X, τ_1, E) . Since $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$, then $\{(F_i, E) \mid i \in I\}$ is a soft RSO -cover of \tilde{X} by RSO soft sets of (X, τ_2, E) . But (X, τ_2, E) is soft RS -compact. Therefore $(X, E) \subseteq (F_{i_1}, E) \cup \dots \cup (F_{i_n}, E)$, for some $i_1, \dots, i_n \in I$. Hence (X, τ_1, E) is soft RS -compact. \square

Let (F, E) be a soft set over X and Y be a nonempty subset of X . Then the sub-soft set of (F, E) over Y denoted by $({}^Y F, E)$ is defined as follows ${}^Y F(e) = Y \cap F(e)$, for each $e \in E$. In other words $({}^Y F, E) = \tilde{Y} \cap (F, E)$. Now, suppose that (X, τ, E) is a sts over X and Y is a nonempty subset of X . Then $\tau_Y = \{({}^Y F, E) \mid (F, E) \in \tau\}$, is said to be soft relative topology on Y and (Y, τ_Y, E) is called a soft subspace of (X, τ, E) . Here, we exhibit a criterion that implies \tilde{Y} is soft RS -compact by soft RSO covers of \tilde{Y} , that all of members are RSO soft sets in X .

Theorem 3.6. *Let (Y, τ_Y, E) be a soft subspace of a soft space (X, τ, E) . Then (Y, τ_Y, E) is soft RS -compact if and only if every cover of \tilde{Y} by RSO soft sets in X contains a finite subcover.*

Proof. Let (Y, τ_Y, E) be soft RS -compact and $\{(F_i, E) \mid i \in I\}$ be a cover of \tilde{Y} by RSO soft sets in X . By Propositions 2.1 and 2.2, we can see that $\{({}^Y F_i, E) \mid i \in I\}$ is a soft RSO cover of \tilde{Y} . Therefore

$$(Y, E) \subseteq ({}^Y F_{i_1}, E) \cup \dots \cup ({}^Y F_{i_n}, E),$$

for some $i_1, \dots, i_n \in I$. This implies that $\{(F_{i_k}, E)\}_{k=1}^n$ is a subcover of \tilde{Y} by RSO soft sets in X .

Conversely, let $\{({}^Y F_i, E) \mid i \in I\}$ be a soft RSO cover of \tilde{Y} . It is easy to see that $\{(F_i, E) \mid i \in I\}$ is a cover of \tilde{Y} by RSO soft sets in X . Then we can write

$$Y \subseteq (F_{i_1}, E) \cup \dots \cup (F_{i_n}, E),$$

for some $i_1, \dots, i_n \in I$. Therefore $\{({}^Y F_{i_k}, E)\}_{k=1}^n$ is a subcover of \tilde{Y} . Hence (Y, τ_Y, E) is soft RS -compact. \square

Definition 3.3. A soft space (X, τ, E) is said to be soft RS -Hausdorff if for each pair x, y of distinct points of X , there exist disjoint RSO soft sets containing x and y , respectively.

Theorem 3.7. *Every soft RS -compact subspace of a soft RS -Hausdorff space is soft RSC .*

Proof. Let (Y, τ_Y, E) be a soft RS -compact subspace of soft RS -Hausdorff space (X, τ, E) . Let $x \in (X, E) - (Y, E)$. Then for all $y \in (Y, E)$, $x \neq y$. Therefore, there exist RSO soft sets (U_y, E) and (U_{xy}, E) containing x and y , respectively such that $(U_y, E) \cap (U_{xy}, E) = \Phi$. Obviously, $\{(U_{xy}, E) | y \in Y\}$ is a cover of \tilde{Y} by RSO soft sets in X . By Theorem 3.6, we have $(Y, E) \subseteq (U_{xy_1}, E) \cup \dots \cup (U_{xy_n}, E)$ for some $y_1, \dots, y_n \in Y$. Now, $x \in (U_{y_1}, E) \cap \dots \cap (U_{y_n}, E) = (U_x, E)$ and Proposition 2.2 implies that $(U_x, E) \cap (Y, E) = (\Phi, E)$. Hence $x \in (U_x, E) \subseteq (X, E) - (Y, E)$. Then $(X, E) - (Y, E) = \bigcup_{x \in X-Y} (U_x, E)$. Therefore $(X, E) - (Y, E)$ is soft RSO . Hence (Y, E) is soft RSC . \square

Now, we consider the countably soft RS -compact spaces in soft topology. A soft topological space (X, τ, E) is said to be countably soft RS -compact if every countable soft RSO cover of \tilde{X} contains a finite subcover of \tilde{X} . Obviously, every soft RS -compact space is countably soft RS -compact.

There is a criterion for a soft space to be countable soft RS -compact in terms of soft RSC sets rather than soft RSO sets. First we have a definition.

A collection \mathcal{A} of soft set is said to have the FIP if for every finite sub-collection $\{(A_1, E), \dots, (A_n, E)\}$ of \mathcal{A} , the intersection $(A_1, E) \cap \dots \cap (A_n, E)$ is non-null.

Theorem 3.8. *A sts is countably soft RS -compact if and only if every countable family of soft RSC sets with the FIP has a non-null intersection.*

Proof. Let the soft space (X, τ, E) be countably soft RS -compact. Let the family $\{(F_i, E)\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ of RSC soft sets have the FIP. If $\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (F_i, E) = (\Phi, E)$ by Proposition 2.2, $\{(F_i, E)'\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ is a countable soft RSO cover of \tilde{X} . Therefore $\tilde{X} = (F_{i_1}, E)' \cup \dots \cup (F_{i_k}, E)'$, for some $i_1, \dots, i_k \in N$. Now, De Morgan laws and Proposition 2.2 imply that $(F_{i_1}, E) \cap \dots \cap (F_{i_k}, E) = (\Phi, E)$. This is a contradiction.

Conversely, Let $\{(F_i, E)\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ be a countable soft RSO -cover of \tilde{X} without any sub-cover. Then $\{(F_i, E)'\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ is a family of RSC soft sets over X such that $\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (F_i, E)' = (\Phi, E)$. Let i_1, \dots, i_k be arbitrary positive integers. If $(F_{i_1}, E)' \cap \dots \cap (F_{i_k}, E)' = (\Phi, E)$ then $\tilde{X} = (F_{i_1}, E) \cup \dots \cup (F_{i_k}, E)$, that is impossible. Therefore $(F_{i_1}, E)' \cap \dots \cap (F_{i_k}, E)' \neq (\Phi, E)$ for each $i_1, \dots, i_k \in N$. This shows that $\{(F_i, E)'\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ have the FIP. Therefore $\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (F_i, E)' \neq (\Phi, E)$. This is a contradiction. \square

An immediate result of previous theorem is the following.

Corollary 3.9. *A soft space (X, τ, E) is countably soft RS -compact if and only if every nested sequence $(F_1, E) \supseteq (F_2, E) \supseteq \dots$ of nonnull RSC soft sets over X has a non-null intersection.*

Proof. Let (X, τ, E) is countably soft RS -compact. The collection $\{(F_i, E)\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ have the FIP. Therefore $\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (F_i, E) \neq (\Phi, E)$. Conversely, let $\{(C_i, E)\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ be a collection of RSC soft sets with the FIP. By Proposition 2.2, we construct nested sequence $(F_1, E) \supseteq (F_2, E) \supseteq \dots$ of non-null RSC soft sets by setting $(F_i, E) = (C_1, E) \cap \dots \cap (C_i, E)$, for each positive integer i . By the hypothesis $\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (F_i, E) = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (C_i, E) \neq (\Phi, E)$. Now, Theorem 3.8 implies that (X, τ, E) is countably soft RS -compact. \square

4. SOFT REGULAR SEMI CONNECTEDNESS

Definition 4.1. Two soft sets (L, A) and (H, B) are said to be disjoint if $(L, A)(x) \cap (H, B)(y) = \Phi \forall x \in A, y \in B$.

Definition 4.2. A soft RS -separation of sts (X, τ, E) is a pair $(L, A), (H, B)$ of disjoint nonnull RSO soft sets whose union is (X, E) .

If there doesn't exist a soft RS -separation of (X, E) , then the sts is said to be soft RS -connected, otherwise soft RS -disconnected.

Example 4.3. Let $X = \{h_1, h_2\}$, $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$, and $\tau = \{\Phi, \tilde{X}, (F_1, E), (F_2, E)\}$, where $(F_1, E), (F_2, E)$ are soft sets over X defined as follows:

$$F_1(e_1) = \{h_1\}, F_1(e_2) = \{h_2\}$$

$$F_2(e_1) = \{h_2\}, F_2(e_2) = \{h_1\}$$

Then τ defines a soft topology on X . So $(F_1, E), (F_2, E)$ are RSO soft sets in (X, E) but $(F_1, E) \tilde{\cap} (F_2, E) = (\Phi, E)$, so there is a soft RS -separation of (X, E) and hence is soft RS -disconnected.

Theorem 4.1. If the soft sets (L, A) and (G, C) form a soft RS -separation of (X, E) , and if (Y, B) is a soft RS -connected subspace of (X, E) , then $(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} (L, A)$ or $(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$.

Proof. Since (L, A) and (G, C) are disjoint RSO soft sets, so are $(L, A) \tilde{\cap} (Y, B)$ and $(G, C) \tilde{\cap} (Y, B)$ and their soft union gives (Y, B) , i.e., they would constitute a soft RS -separation of (Y, B) , a contradiction. Hence, one of $(L, A) \tilde{\cap} (Y, B)$ and $(G, C) \tilde{\cap} (Y, B)$ is empty and so (Y, B) is entirely contained in one of them. \square

Theorem 4.2. Let (Y, B) be a soft RS -connected subspace of (X, E) and (K, D) be a soft set in (X, E) such that $(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} (K, D) \tilde{\subseteq} cl(Y, B)$, then (K, D) is also soft RS -connected.

Proof. Let the soft set (K, D) satisfies the hypothesis. If possible, let (F, A) and (G, C) form a soft RS -separation of (K, D) . Then, by Theorem 4.1, $(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} (F, A)$ or $(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$. Let $(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} (F, A) \Rightarrow r_{sscl}(Y, B) \tilde{\subseteq} r_{sscl}(F, A)$; since $r_{sscl}(F, A)$ and (G, C) are disjoint, (Y, B) cannot intersect (G, C) . This contradicts the fact that (G, C) is a nonempty subset of $(Y, B) \Rightarrow \nexists$ a soft RS -separation of (K, D) and hence is soft RS -connected. \square

Theorem 4.3. A sts (X, τ, E) is soft RS -disconnected $\Leftrightarrow \exists$ a nonnull proper soft subset of (X, E) which is both RSO and RSC soft sets.

Proof. Let (K, D) be a nonnull proper soft subset of (X, E) which is both RSO and RSC soft sets. Now $(H, C) = (K, D)'$ is nonnull proper subset of (X, E) which is also both RSO and RSC soft sets $\Rightarrow r_{sscl}(K, D) = (K, D)$ and $r_{sscl}(H, C) = (H, C) \Rightarrow (X, E)$ can be expressed as the soft union of two RS -separated soft sets $(K, D), (H, C)$ and so, is soft RS -disconnected.

Conversely, let (X, E) be soft RS -disconnected $\Rightarrow \exists$ nonnull soft subsets (K, D) and (H, C) such that $r_{sscl}(K, D) \tilde{\cap} (H, C) = (\Phi, E)$, $(K, D) \tilde{\cap} r_{sscl}(H, C) = (\Phi, E)$ and $(K, D) \tilde{\cup} (H, C) = (X, E)$. Now $(K, D) \tilde{\subseteq} r_{sscl}(K, D)$ and $r_{sscl}(K, D) \tilde{\cap} (H, C) = (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow (K, D) \tilde{\cap} (H, C) = (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow (H, C) = (K, D)'$. Then $(K, D) \tilde{\cup} r_{sscl}(H, C) = (X, E)$ and $(K, D) \tilde{\cap} r_{sscl}(H, C) = (\Phi, E) \Rightarrow (K, D) = (r_{sscl}(H, C))'$ and similarly $(H, C) = (r_{sscl}(K, D))' \Rightarrow (K, D), (H, C)$ are RSO soft sets being the complements of RSC soft sets. Also $(H, C) = (K, D)' \Rightarrow$ they are also soft RSC . \square

Theorem 4.4. SRS -continuous image of a soft RS -connected sts is soft connected.

Proof. Let $f : SS(X, E) \rightarrow SS(Y, E)$ be a *SRS*-continuous function where (X, τ, E) a soft *RS*-connected sts and (Y, δ, E) is a sts. We wish to show $f(X, E)$ is soft connected. Suppose $f(X, E) = (K, D) \dot{\cup} (H, C)$ be a soft separation. i.e., (K, D) and (H, C) are disjoint soft open sets whose union is $f(X, E) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(K, D)$ and $f^{-1}(H, C)$ are disjoint *RSO* soft sets whose union is (X, E) . So, $f^{-1}(K, D)$ and $f^{-1}(H, C)$ form a soft *RS*-separation of (X, E) , a contradiction. \square

Theorem 4.5. *SRS-irresolute image of a soft RS-connected sts is soft RS-connected.*

Proof. Similar to that of Theorem 4.4 \square

5. SOFT REGULAR SEMI SEPARATION AXIOMS

Soft separation axioms for sts were studied by Shabir et al. [23]. Here we consider separation axioms for sts's using *RSO* and *RSC* soft sets.

Definition 5.1. Two soft sets (G, C) and (H, B) are said to be distinct if $G(e) \cap H(e) = \Phi, \forall e \in B \cap C$.

Definition 5.2. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be a soft *RS-T₀* space if for two disjoint soft points $G(e)$ and $F(e)$, \exists a *RSO* soft set containing one but not the other.

Example 5.3. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$, and $\tau = \{\Phi, \tilde{X}, (F_1, E), (F_2, E)\}$, where $(F_1, E), (F_2, E)$ are soft sets over X defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(e_1) &= \{x_1\}, F_1(e_2) = \{x_1\} \\ F_2(e_1) &= \{x_2\}, F_2(e_2) = \{x_2\} \end{aligned}$$

Then τ defines a soft topology on X . Also (X, τ, E) is soft *RS-T₀* space, since $x_1, x_2 \in X, x_1 \neq x_2, \exists$ a *RSO* soft sets $(F_1, E), (F_2, E)$ such that $x_1 \in (F_1, E)$ and $x_2 \notin (F_1, E)$ or $x_1 \notin (F_2, E)$ and $x_2 \in (F_2, E)$.

Theorem 5.1. Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and the soft points $F(e), G(e)$ of (X, E) such that $F(e) \neq G(e)$. If there exists *RSO* soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $F(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)$ and $G(e) \not\tilde{\in} (H, D)$ or $G(e) \tilde{\in} (H, D)$ and $F(e) \not\tilde{\in} (G, C)$. Then (X, τ, E) is soft *RS-T₀* space.

Proof. Let $F(e)$ and $G(e)$ be two distinct soft points in a sts (X, τ, E) . Let (G, C) and (H, D) be *RSO* soft sets such that either $F(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)$ and $G(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)'$ or $G(e) \tilde{\in} (H, D)$ and $F(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)'$. If $F(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)$ and $G(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)'$. Then $G(e) \tilde{\in} (G, C)'$ for all $e \in C$, this implies that $G(e) \not\tilde{\in} (G, C)$ for all $e \in C$. Therefore, $G(e) \not\tilde{\in} (G, C)$. Similarly, if $G(e) \tilde{\in} (H, D)$ and $F(e) \tilde{\in} (H, D)'$, then $F(e) \not\tilde{\in} (H, D)$. Hence (X, τ, E) is soft *RS-T₀* space. \square

Theorem 5.2. A sts is a soft *RS-T₀* space if the soft regular semiclosures of distinct soft points are distinct.

Proof. Let $F(e)$ and $H(e)$ be two distinct soft points with distinct soft regular semiclosures in a sts (X, τ, E) . If possible, suppose we had $F(e) \tilde{\in} r_{sscl}(H(e))$, then $r_{sscl}(F(e)) \tilde{\subset} r_{sscl}(H(e))$, a contradiction. So $F(e) \not\tilde{\in} r_{sscl}(H(e)) \Rightarrow (r_{sscl}(H(e)))'$ is a *RSO* soft set containing $F(e)$ but not $H(e)$. Hence (X, τ, E) is a soft *RS-T₀* space. \square

Theorem 5.3. A soft subspace of a soft *RS-T₀* space is soft *RS-T₀*.

Proof. Let (Y, B) be a soft subspace of a soft *RS-T₀* space (X, E) and let $F(e), G(e)$ be two distinct soft points of (Y, B) . Then these soft points are also in $(X, E) \Rightarrow \exists$ a *RSO* soft set (H, D) containing one of these soft points, say $F(e)$, but not the other $\Rightarrow (H, D) \cap (Y, B)$ is a *RSO* soft set containing $F(e)$ but not the other. \square

Definition 5.4. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be a soft $RS-T_1$ -space if for two distinct soft points $F(e), G(e)$ of (X, E) , \exists RSO soft sets (H, D) and (G, C) such that $F(e) \tilde{\in}(H, D)$ and $G(e) \not\tilde{\in}(H, D)$;
 $G(e) \tilde{\in}(G, C)$ and $F(e) \not\tilde{\in}(G, C)$.

Example 5.5. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$, $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$ and $\tau = \{\Phi, X, (F_1, E), (F_2, E), (F_3, E), (F_4, E), (F_5, E), (F_6, E)\}$ where
 $F_1(e_1) = \{x_1, x_2\}$, $F_1(e_2) = \{x_1, x_3\}$
 $F_2(e_1) = \{x_2, x_3\}$, $F_2(e_2) = \{x_1, x_2\}$
 $F_3(e_1) = \{x_1, x_3\}$, $F_3(e_2) = \{x_2, x_3\}$
 $F_4(e_1) = \{x_2\}$, $F_4(e_2) = \{x_1\}$
 $F_5(e_1) = \{x_3\}$, $F_5(e_2) = \{x_2\}$
 $F_6(e_1) = \{x_1\}$, $F_6(e_2) = \{x_3\}$

Then (X, τ, E) is a sts over X . We note that (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_1$ space, because there exists RSO soft sets $(F_1, E), (F_2, E), (F_3, E)$ such that $x_1 \in (F_1, E)$, $x_2 \notin (F_1, E)$ and $x_2 \in (F_2, E)$, $x_1 \notin (F_2, E)$; $x_1 \in (F_1, E)$, $x_3 \notin (F_1, E)$ and $x_3 \in (F_3, E)$, $x_1 \notin (F_3, E)$; $x_2 \in (F_2, E)$, $x_3 \notin (F_2, E)$ and $x_3 \in (F_3, E)$, $x_2 \notin (F_3, E)$.

Theorem 5.4. Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and the soft points $F(e), G(e)$ of (X, E) such that $F(e) \neq G(e)$. If there exists RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $F(e) \tilde{\in}(G, C)$ and $G(e) \not\tilde{\in}(H, D)$ and $G(e) \tilde{\in}(H, D)$ and $F(e) \not\tilde{\in}(G, C)$. Then (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_1$ space.

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 5.1 □

Theorem 5.5. If every soft point of a sts (X, τ, E) is a RSC soft set then (X, τ, E) is a soft $RS-T_1$ space.

Proof. Let $F(e)$ and $G(e)$ be two distinct soft points of $(X, E) \Rightarrow (F(e))', (G(e))'$ are RSO soft sets such that $G(e) \tilde{\in}(F(e))'$ and $G(e) \not\tilde{\in}F(e)$; $F(e) \tilde{\in}(G(e))'$ and $F(e) \not\tilde{\in}G(e)$. □

Theorem 5.6. A soft subspace of a soft $RS-T_1$ space is soft $RS-T_1$.

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 5.3 □

Definition 5.6. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be a soft $RS-T_2$ space if and only if for distinct soft points $F(e), G(e)$ of (X, E) , \exists disjoint RSO soft sets (H, B) and (G, C) such that $F(e) \tilde{\in}(H, B)$ and $G(e) \tilde{\in}(G, C)$.

Example 5.7. In Example 5.3, (X, τ, E) is also soft $RS-T_2$ space.

Example 5.8. Let us consider the soft topology (X, τ, E) on Example 5.5. Now we show that (X, τ, E) is not a soft $RS-T_2$ space. For $x_1 \neq x_2$, $x_1 \in (F_1, E)$, $x_2 \in (F_2, E)$ and $(F_1, E) \tilde{\cap}(F_2, E) = \{\{x_2\}, \{x_1\}\} \neq (\Phi, E)$. Then (X, τ, E) is not soft $RS-T_2$ space.

Theorem 5.7. A soft subspace of a soft $RS-T_2$ space is soft $RS-T_2$.

Proof. Let (X, τ, E) be a soft $RS-T_2$ space and (Y, B) be a soft subspace of (X, E) , where $B \subseteq E$ and $Y \subseteq X$. Let $F(e)$ and $G(e)$ be two distinct soft points of (Y, B) . (X, E) is soft $RS-T_2 \Rightarrow \exists$ two disjoint RSO soft sets (H, D) and (G, C) such that $F(e) \tilde{\in}(H, D)$, $G(e) \tilde{\in}(G, C)$. Then $(H, D) \tilde{\cap}(Y, B)$ and $(G, C) \tilde{\cap}(Y, B)$ are RSO soft sets satisfying the requirements for (Y, B) to be a soft $RS-T_2$ space. □

Theorem 5.8. A sts (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_2$ if and only if for distinct soft points $G(e), F(e)$ of (X, E) , \exists a RSO soft set (F, A) containing $G(e)$ but not $F(e)$ such that $F(e) \notin \widetilde{rsscl}(F, A)$.

Proof. Let $G(e), F(e)$ be distinct soft points in a soft $RS-T_2$ space (X, τ, E) .

(\Rightarrow) \exists distinct RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $F(e) \in (G, C)$, $G(e) \in (H, D)$. This implies $G(e) \in (G, C)'$. So, $(G, C)'$ is a RSC soft set containing $G(e)$ but not $F(e)$ and $rsscl(G, C)' = (G, C)'$.

(\Leftarrow) Take a pair of distinct soft points $G(e)$ and $F(e)$ of (X, E) , \exists a RSO soft set (H, D) containing $G(e)$ but not $F(e)$ such that $F(e) \notin \widetilde{rsscl}(H, D) \Rightarrow F(e) \in (rsscl(H, D))' \Rightarrow (H, D)$ and $(rsscl(H, D))'$ are disjoint RSO soft set containing $G(e)$ and $F(e)$ respectively. \square

Definition 5.9. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be a soft RS -regular space if for every soft point $F(e)$ and RSC soft set (L, A) not containing $F(e)$, \exists disjoint RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $F(e) \in (G, C)$ and $(L, A) \subseteq (H, D)$, where $C, D \in E$.

A soft RS -regular with soft $RS-T_1$ space is called a soft $RS-T_3$ space.

Example 5.10. Let us consider the soft topology (X, τ, E) on Exanple 5.5. We know that (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_1$ space from Example 5.5. Now we show that (X, τ, E) is not a soft $RS-T_3$ space. For this,

$$\tau' = \{\Phi, X, (F_1, E)', (F_2, E)', (F_3, E)', (F_4, E)', (F_5, E)', (F_6, E)'\}$$

where,

$$F_1'(e_1) = \{x_3\}, F_1'(e_2) = \{x_2\}$$

$$F_2'(e_1) = \{x_1\}, F_2'(e_2) = \{x_3\}$$

$$F_3'(e_1) = \{x_2\}, F_3'(e_2) = \{x_1\}$$

$$F_4'(e_1) = \{x_1, x_3\}, F_4'(e_2) = \{x_2, x_3\}$$

$$F_5'(e_1) = \{x_1, x_2\}, F_5'(e_2) = \{x_1, x_3\}$$

$$F_6'(e_1) = \{x_2, x_3\}, F_6'(e_2) = \{x_1, x_2\}$$

Then, $x_1 \in (F_1, E)$, a RSC soft set $(G, E) = (F_1, E)'$ and $x_1 \notin (G, E)$, then there exists a RSO soft sets (F_2, E) and (F_5, E) such that $x_1 \in (F_2, E)$ and $(G, E) \subseteq (F_5, E)$ but $(F_2, E) \cap (F_5, E) = \{\{x_3\}, \{x_2\}\} \neq (\Phi, E)$. Then (X, τ, E) is not soft RS -regular space, so (X, τ, E) is not a soft $RS-T_3$ space.

Remark. It can be shown that the property of being soft $RS-T_3$ is hereditary.

Remark. Soft $RS-T_3 \Rightarrow$ soft $RS-T_2 \Rightarrow$ soft $RS-T_1 \Rightarrow$ soft $RS-T_0$.

Definition 5.11. A cover of a soft set is said to be a soft RSO -cover if every member of the cover is a RSO soft set.

Definition 5.12. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be soft RS -compact if each soft RSO -cover of (X, E) has a finite subcover.

Theorem 5.9. A sts which is both soft RS -compact and soft $RS-T_2$ is soft $RS-T_3$.

Proof. It suffices to show every soft RS -compact sts is soft RS -regular. Let $F(e)$ be a soft point and (H, D) be a RSC soft set not containing the point $\Rightarrow F(e) \in (H, D)'$. Now for each soft point $G(e)$, \exists disjoint RSO soft sets (G, C_1) and (G, C_2) such that $G(e) \in (G, C_1)$ and $F(e) \in (G, C_2)$. So, the collection $\{(G_i, C)|i \in I\}$ forms a RSO -cover of (H, D) . Now (H, D) is a RSC soft set $\Rightarrow (H, D)$ is soft RS -compact. Hence \exists a finite subfamily I_0 of I such that $(H, D) \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I_0} (G_i, C)$. Take $(K, B) = \bigcap_{i=1}^n (K_i, B)$ and

$(G, C) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n (G_i, C)$. Then (K, B) , (G, C) are disjoint *R**S**O* sets such that $F(e)$ is a soft point of (K, B) and $(L, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$. \square

Proposition 5.10. *Let (X, τ, E) be a sts, (G, C) be a *R**S**C* soft set in (X, E) and $F(e)$ be a soft point such that $F(e) \notin (G, C)$. If (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*-regular space, then there exists a *R**S**O* soft set (K, D) such that $F(e) \widetilde{\in} (K, D)$ and $(K, D) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$.*

Proof. It is obvious from Definition 5.9 \square

Proposition 5.11. *Let (X, τ, E) be a sts, $(G, C) \widetilde{\in} SS(X, E)$ and $x \in X$. Then:*

- (i) $x \in (G, C)$ if and only if $(x, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$.
- (ii) If $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$, then $x \notin (G, C)$.

Proof. Obvious. \square

Theorem 5.12. *Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and $x \in X$. If (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*-regular space, then:*

- (1) $x \notin (G, C)$ if and only if $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$ for every *R**S**C* soft set (G, C) .
- (2) $x \notin (H, D)$ if and only if $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$ for every *R**S**O* soft set (H, D) .

Proof. (i) Let (G, C) be a *R**S**C* soft set such that $x \notin (G, C)$. Since (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*-regular space. Then by Proposition 5.10 there exists a *R**S**O* soft set (H, D) such that $x \in (H, D)$ and $(G, C) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. It follows that $(x, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ from Proposition 5.11(1). Hence $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$. Conversely, if $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$, then $x \notin (G, C)$ from Proposition 5.11(2).

(ii) Let (H, D) be a *R**S**O* soft set such that $x \notin (H, D)$. If $x \notin F(e)$ for all $e \in E$, then we get the proof. If $x \notin F(e_1)$ and $x \in F(e_2)$ for some $e_1, e_2 \in E$, then $x \in (F(e_1))'$ and $x \notin (F(e_2))'$ for some $e_1, e_2 \in E$. This means that, $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) \neq (\Phi, E)$. Hence $(H, D)'$ is *R**S**C* soft set such that $x \notin (H, D)'$. It follows by (1) $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D)' = (\Phi, E)$. This implies that, $(x, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and so $x \in (H, D)$, which is contradiction with $x \notin F(e_1)$ for some $e_1 \in E$. Therefore, $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Conversely, if $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$, then it is obvious that $x \notin (H, D)$. This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 5.13. *Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and $x \in X$. If (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*-regular space, then the following are equivalent:*

- (1) (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*- T_1 space.
- (2) $\forall x, y \in X$ such that $x \neq y$, there exist *R**S**O* soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $(x, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$ and $(y, E) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$ and $(y, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$.

Proof. It is obvious from Theorem 5.12 \square

Theorem 5.14. *Let (X, τ, E) be a sts and $x \in X$. Then the following are equivalent:*

- (1) (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*-regular space.
- (2) For every *R**S**C* soft set (G, C) such that $(x, E) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$, there exist *R**S**O* soft sets (L, A) and (H, D) such that $(x, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (L, A)$, $(G, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and $(L, A) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2): Let (G, C) be a RSC soft set such that $(x, E)\tilde{\cap}(G, C) = (\Phi, E)$. Then $x \notin (G, C)$ from Theorem 5.12(1). It follows by (1), there exist RSO soft sets (L, A) and (H, D) such that $x \in (L, A)$, $(G, C)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)$ and $(L, A)\tilde{\cap}(H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. This means that, $(x, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(L, A)$, $(G, C)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)$ and $(L, A)\tilde{\cap}(H, D) = (\Phi, E)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1): Let (G, C) be a RSC soft set such that $x \notin (G, C)$. Then $(x, E)\tilde{\cap}(G, C) = (\Phi, E)$ from Theorem 5.12(1). It follows by (2), there exist RSO soft sets (L, A) and (H, D) such that $(x, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(L, A)$, $(G, C)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)$ and $(L, A)\tilde{\cap}(H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Hence $(x, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(L, A)$, $(G, C)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)$ and $(L, A)\tilde{\cap}(H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Thus, (X, τ, E) is soft RS -regular space. \square

Theorem 5.15. *Let (X, τ, E) be a sts. If (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_3$ space, then $\forall x \in X$, (x, E) is RSC soft set.*

Proof. We want to prove that (x, E) is RSC soft set, which is sufficient to prove that $(x, E)'$ is RSO soft set for all $y \in \{x\}'$. Since (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_3$ -space, then there exist RSO soft sets $(H, D)_y$ and (G, C) such that $(y, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)_y$ and $(x, E)\tilde{\cap}(H, D)_y = (\Phi, E)$ and $(x, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(G, C)$ and $(y, E)\tilde{\cap}(G, C) = (\Phi, E)$. It follows that $\bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (H, D)_y \tilde{\subseteq}(x, E)'$. Now we want to prove that $(x, E)'\tilde{\subseteq} \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (H, D)_y$. Let $\bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (H, D)_y = (F, A)$, where $F(e) = \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (F(e)_y)$ for all $e \in E$. Since $(x, E)'(e) = \{x\}'$ for all $e \in E$ from Definition 15 in [23]. So, for all $y \in \{x\}'$ and $e \in E$, $(x, E)'(e) = \{x\}' = \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } \{y\} = \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (y, E)(e)\tilde{\subseteq} \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } F(e)_y = F(e)$. Thus, $(x, E)'\tilde{\subseteq} \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (H, D)_y$ from definition of soft subsets and so $(x, E)' = \bigcup_{y \in \{x\}' } (H, D)_y$. This means that, $(x, E)'$ is RSO soft set for all $y \in \{x\}'$. Therefore, (x, E) is RSC soft set. \square

Theorem 5.16. *Every soft $RS-T_3$ space is soft $RS-T_2$ space.*

Proof. Let (X, τ, E) be a soft $RS-T_3$ space and $x, y \in X$ such that $x \neq y$. By Theorem 5.15, (y, E) is RSC soft set and $x \notin (y, E)$. It follows from the soft RS -regularity, there exist RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $x \in (G, C)$, $(y, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)$ and $(G, C)\tilde{\cap}(H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Thus, $x \in (G, C)$, $y \in (y, E)\tilde{\subseteq}(H, D)$ and $(G, C)\tilde{\cap}(H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Therefore, (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_2$ space. \square

Theorem 5.17. *A soft subspace (Y, τ_Y, E) of a soft $RS-T_3$ space (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_3$.*

Proof. By Theorem 5.3 (Y, τ_Y, E) is soft $RS-T_1$ space. Now we want to prove that (Y, τ_Y, E) is soft RS -regular space. Let $y \in Y$ and (G, C) be a RSC soft set in Y such that $y \notin (G, C)$. Then $(G, C) = (Y, E)\tilde{\cap}(H, D)$ for some RSC soft set (H, D) in X from Theorem 2.4 Hence $y \notin (Y, E)\tilde{\cap}(H, D)$. But $y \in (Y, E)$, so $y \notin (H, D)$. Since (X, τ, E) is soft $RS-T_3$ -space, so there exist RSO soft sets (H_1, D) and (H_2, D) in X such that $y \in (H_1, D)$, $(H, D)\tilde{\subseteq}(H_2, D)$ and $(H_1, D)\tilde{\cap}(H_2, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Take $(G_1, C) = (Y, E)\tilde{\cap}(H_1, D)$ and $(G_2, C) = (Y, E)\tilde{\cap}(H_2, D)$, then (G_1, C) , (G_2, C) are RSO soft sets in Y such that $y \in (G_1, C)$, $(G, C)\tilde{\subseteq}(Y, E)\tilde{\cap}(H_2, D) = (G_2, C)$ and $(G_1, C)\tilde{\cap}(G_2, C)\tilde{\subseteq}(H_1, D)\tilde{\cap}(H_2, D) = (\Phi, E)$. Thus, (Y, τ_Y, E) is soft $RS-T_3$ space. \square

Definition 5.13. A sts (X, τ, E) is said to be a soft RS -normal space if for every pair of disjoint RSC soft sets (G_1, C) and (G_2, C) , \exists two disjoint RSO soft sets (H_1, D) , (H_2, D) such that $(G_1, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_1, D)$ and $(G_2, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_2, D)$.

A soft RS -normal with T_1 -space is called a soft $RS-T_4$ -space.

Example 5.14. Let us consider the soft topology (X, τ, E) on Example 5.5. We know that (X, τ, E) is a soft $RS-T_1$ -space from Example 5.5. Now we show that (X, τ, E) is a soft $RS-T_4$ -space. Here, (F_4, E) , (F_5, E) , (F_6, E) are soft RSC sets such that $(F_5, E) \widetilde{\cap} (F_6, E) = (\Phi, E)$, $(F_5, E) \widetilde{\cap} (F_4, E) = (\Phi, E)$, $(F_4, E) \widetilde{\cap} (F_6, E) = (\Phi, E)$. Then there exist RSO soft sets (F_4, E) , (F_5, E) , (F_6, E) such that $(F_5, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (F_5, E)$, $(F_6, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (F_6, E)$, $(F_4, E) \widetilde{\subseteq} (F_4, E)$ and $(F_5, E) \widetilde{\cap} (F_6, E) = (\Phi, E)$, $(F_5, E) \widetilde{\cap} (F_4, E) = (\Phi, E)$, $(F_4, E) \widetilde{\cap} (F_6, E) = (\Phi, E)$. And then, (X, τ, E) is a soft RS -normal space. Therefore, (X, τ, E) is a soft $RS-T_4$ space.

Remark. In Examples 5.10 and 5.14 shows that every soft $RS-T_4$ space is need not be soft $RS-T_3$.

Theorem 5.18. A sts (X, τ, E) is soft RS -normal if and only if for any RSC soft set (L, A) and RSO soft set (G, C) containing (L, A) , there exists an RSO soft set (H, D) such that $(L, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and $rsscl(H, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$.

Proof. Let (X, τ, E) be RS -normal space and (L, A) be a RSC soft set and (G, C) be a RSO soft set containing $(L, A) \Rightarrow (L, A)$ and $(G, C)'$ are disjoint RSC soft sets $\Rightarrow \exists$ two disjoint RSO soft sets (H_1, D) , (H_2, D) such that $(L, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_1, D)$ and $(G, C)' \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_2, D)$. Now $(H_1, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_2, D)' \Rightarrow rsscl(H_1, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} rsscl(H_2, D)' = (H_2, D)'$. Also, $(G, C)' \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_2, D) \Rightarrow (H_2, D)' \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C) \Rightarrow rsscl(H_1, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$.

Conversely, let (F, A) and (K, B) be any disjoint pair RSC soft sets $\Rightarrow (F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (K, B)'$, then by hypothesis there exists an RSO soft set (H, D) such that $(F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and $rsscl(H, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} (K, B)' \Rightarrow (K, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} (rsscl(H, D))' \Rightarrow (H, D)$ and $(rsscl(H, D))'$ are disjoint RSO soft sets such that $(F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and $(K, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} (rsscl(H, D))'$. \square

Theorem 5.19. Let $f : SS(X, E) \rightarrow SS(Y, E')$ be a soft surjective function which is both SRS -irresolute and $SRSI$ -open where (X, τ, E) and (Y, σ, E') are soft topological spaces. If (X, E) is soft RS -normal space then so is (Y, E') .

Proof. Take a pair of disjoint RSC soft sets (F, A) and (K, B) of $(Y, E') \Rightarrow f^{-1}(F, A)$ and $f^{-1}(K, B)$ are disjoint RSC soft sets of $(X, E) \Rightarrow \exists$ disjoint RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $f^{-1}(F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (G, C)$ and $f^{-1}(K, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D) \Rightarrow (F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} f(G, C)$ and $(K, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} f(H, D) \Rightarrow f(G, C)$ and $f(H, D)$ are disjoint RSO soft sets of (Y, E') containing (F, A) and (K, B) respectively. Hence the result. \square

Theorem 5.20. A regular semiclosed soft subspace of a soft RS -normal space is soft RS -normal.

Proof. Let (Y, E') be a regular semiclosed soft subspace of a soft RS -normal space (X, E) . Take a disjoint pair (F, A) and (G, C) of RSC soft sets of $(Y, E') \Rightarrow \exists$ disjoint RSC soft sets (K, B) and (H, D) such that $(F, A) = (K, B) \widetilde{\cap} (Y, E')$, $(G, C) = (H, D) \widetilde{\cap} (Y, E')$. Now by soft RS -normality of (X, E) , \exists disjoint RSO soft sets (K_1, B) and (H_1, D) such that $(K, B) \widetilde{\subseteq} (K_1, B)$ and $(H, D) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_1, D) \Rightarrow (F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (K_1, B) \widetilde{\cap} (Y, E')$ and $(G, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H_1, D) \widetilde{\cap} (Y, E')$. \square

Theorem 5.21. Every soft RS -compact with soft $RS-T_2$ space is RS -normal.

Proof. Let (X, τ, E) be a soft RS -compact with soft RS - T_2 space. Take a disjoint pair (F, A) and (K, B) of RSC soft sets. By Theorem 5.9, for each soft point $L(e)$, \exists disjoint RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) such that $L(e) \subseteq (G, C)$ and $(K, B) \subseteq (H, D)$. So the collection $\{(G_i, C) \mid L(e) \subseteq (G_i, C), i \in I\}$ is a RSO -cover of (G, C) . Then by Theorem 5.9, \exists a finite subfamily $\{(G_i, C) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ such that $(G, C) \subseteq \bigcup \{(G_i, C) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Take $(G, C) = \bigcap \{(G_i, C) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $(H, D) = \bigcap \{(H_i, D) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then (G, C) and (H, D) are disjoint RSO soft sets such that $(F, A) \subseteq (G, C)$ and $(K, B) \subseteq (H, D)$. Hence (X, E) is soft RS -normal. \square

6. SOME TYPES OF SOFT FUNCTIONS

Theorem 6.1. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective and $SRSI$ -open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft RS - T_0 space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft RS - T_0 space.*

Proof. Let $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ such that $y_1 \neq y_2$. Since f_{pu} is surjective, then $\exists x_1, x_2 \in X$ such that $u(x_1) = y_1$, $u(x_2) = y_2$ and $x_1 \neq x_2$. By hypothesis, there exist RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) in X such that either $x_1 \in (G, C)$ and $x_2 \notin (G, C)$ or $x_2 \in (H, D)$ and $x_1 \notin (H, D)$. So, either $x_1 \in F(e)$ and $x_2 \notin F(e)$ or $x_2 \in G(e)$ and $x_1 \notin G(e)$ for all $e \in E$. This implies that, either $y_1 = u(x_1) \in u(F(e))$ and $y_2 = u(x_2) \notin u(F(e))$ or $y_2 = u(x_2) \in u(G(e))$ and $y_1 = u(x_1) \notin u(G(e))$ for all $e \in E$. Hence either $y_1 \in f_{pu}(G, C)$ and $y_2 \notin f_{pu}(G, C)$ or $y_2 \in f_{pu}(H, D)$ and $y_1 \notin f_{pu}(H, D)$. Since f_{pu} is $SRSI$ -open function, then $f_{pu}(G, C)$, $f_{pu}(H, D)$ are RSO soft sets in Y . Hence (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft RS - T_0 space. \square

Theorem 6.2. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective and $SRSI$ -open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft RS - T_1 space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft RS - T_1 space.*

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 6.1 \square

Theorem 6.3. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective and $SRSI$ -open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft RS - T_2 space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft RS - T_2 space.*

Proof. $y_1, y_2 \in Y$ such that $y_1 \neq y_2$. Since f_{pu} is surjective, then $\exists x_1, x_2 \in X$ such that $u(x_1) = y_1$, $u(x_2) = y_2$ and $x_1 \neq x_2$. By hypothesis, there exist RSO soft sets (G, C) and (H, D) in X such that $x_1 \in (G, C)$, $x_2 \in (H, D)$ and $(G, C) \tilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$. So, $x_1 \in F(e)$, $x_2 \in G(e)$ and $F(e) \tilde{\cap} G(e) = (\Phi, E)$ for all $e \in E$. This implies that, $y_1 = u(x_1) \in u(F(e))$, $y_2 = u(x_2) \in u(G(e))$ for all $e \in E$. Hence $y_1 \in f_{pu}(G, C)$, $y_2 \in f_{pu}(H, D)$ and $f_{pu}(G, C) \tilde{\cap} f_{pu}(H, D) = f_{pu}[(G, C) \tilde{\cap} (H, D)] = f_{pu}(\Phi, A) = (\Phi, B)$ from Theorem 2.5 Since f_{pu} is $SRSI$ -open function, then $f_{pu}(G, C)$, $f_{pu}(H, D)$ are RSO soft sets in Y . Thus, (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft RS - T_2 space. \square

Theorem 6.4. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective, SRS -irresolute and $SRSI$ -open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft RS -regular space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft RS -regular space.*

Proof. Let (G, C) be a RSC soft set in Y and $y \in Y$ such that $y \notin (G, C)$. Since f_{pu} is surjective and SRS -irresolute, then $\exists x \in X$ such that $u(x) = y$ and $f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C)$ is RSC soft set in X such that $x \notin f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C)$. By hypothesis, there exist RSO soft sets (F, A) and (H, D) in X such that $x \in (F, A)$, $f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C) \subseteq (H, D)$ and $(F, A) \tilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, E)$.

It follows that $x \in F(e)$ for all $e \in E$ and $(G, C) = f_{pu}[f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C)] \widetilde{\subseteq} f_{pu}(H, D)$ from Theorem 2.5. So, $y = u(x_1) \in u[F(e)]$ for all $e \in E$ and $(G, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} f_{pu}(H, D)$. Hence $y \in f_{pu}(F, A)$ and $(G, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} f_{pu}(H, D)$ and $f_{pu}(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} f_{pu}(H, D) = f_{pu}[(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D)] = f_{pu}(\Phi, A) = (\Phi, B)$ from Theorem 2.5 Since f_{pu} is *SRSI*-open function. Then $f_{pu}(F, A)$, $f_{pu}(H, D)$ are *RSO* soft sets in Y . Thus, (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*-regular space. \square

Theorem 6.5. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective, *SRS*-irresolute and *SRSI*-open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft *RS*- T_3 space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*- T_3 space.*

Proof. Since (X, τ_1, A) is soft *RS*- T_3 space, then (X, τ_1, A) is soft *RS*-regular with soft *RS*- T_1 space. It follows that (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*- T_1 space from Theorem 6.4 and soft *RS*-regular space from Theorem 6.4 Hence, (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*- T_3 space. \square

Theorem 6.6. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective, *SRS*-irresolute and *SRSI*-open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft *RS*-normal space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*-normal space.*

Proof. Let (F, A) and (G, C) be *RSC* soft sets in Y such that $(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C) = (\Phi, E)$. Since f_{pu} is *SRS*-irresolute, then $f_{pu}^{-1}(F, A)$ and $f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C)$ are *RSC* soft set in X such that $f_{pu}^{-1}(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C) = f_{pu}^{-1}[(F, A) \widetilde{\cap} (G, C)] = f_{pu}^{-1}(\Phi, E) = (\Phi, A)$ from Theorem 2.5 By hypothesis, there exist *RSO* soft sets (K, B) and (H, D) in X such that $f_{pu}^{-1}(F, A) \widetilde{\subseteq} (K, B)$, $f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C) \widetilde{\subseteq} (H, D)$ and $(K, B) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D) = (\Phi, A)$. It follows that $(F, A) = f_{pu}[f_{pu}^{-1}(F, A)] \widetilde{\subseteq} f_{pu}(K, B)$, $(G, C) = f_{pu}[f_{pu}^{-1}(G, C)] \widetilde{\subseteq} f_{pu}(H, D)$ from Theorem 2.5 and $f_{pu}(K, B) \widetilde{\cap} f_{pu}(H, D) = f_{pu}[(K, B) \widetilde{\cap} (H, D)] = f_{pu}(\Phi, A) = (\Phi, B)$ from Theorem 2.5 Since f_{pu} is *SRSI*-open function. Then $f_{pu}(K, B)$, $f_{pu}(H, D)$ are *RSO* soft sets in Y . Thus, (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*-normal space. \square

Corollary 6.7. *Let (X, τ_1, A) and (Y, τ_2, B) be sts's and $f_{pu} : SS(X, A) \rightarrow SS(Y, B)$ be soft function which is bijective, *SRS*-irresolute and *SRSI*-open. If (X, τ_1, A) is soft *RS*- T_4 space, then (Y, τ_2, B) is also a soft *RS*- T_4 space.*

Proof. It is obvious from Theorem 6.2 and Theorem 6.6 \square

7. CONCLUSION

Topology is an important and major area of mathematics and it can give many relationships between other scientific areas and mathematical models. Recently, many scientists have studied and improved the soft set theory, which is initiated by Molodtsov [19] and easily applied to many problems having uncertainties from social life. In this paper, we introduce the notion of soft regular semi compactness, connectedness and separation axioms. In particular we study the properties of the soft *RS*-regular spaces and soft *RS*-normal spaces. We show that if (x, E) is *RSC* soft set for all $x \in X$ in a sts (X, τ, E) , then (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*- T_1 space. Also, we show that if a sts (X, τ, E) is soft *RS*- T_3 space, then $\forall x \in X$, (x, E) is *RSC* soft set. Also, we show that the property of being soft *RS*- T_i spaces ($i = 1, 2$) is soft topological property under a bijection and irresolute open soft mapping. Further, the properties of being soft *RS*-regular and soft *RS*-normal are soft topological properties under a bijection, *SRS*-irresolute functions and *SRSI*-open functions. Finally, we show that the property of being soft *RS*- T_i spaces ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) is a hereditary property. Similarly other forms of generalized open set can be applied to define different forms of compactness and connectedness. We hope that the results in this paper

will help researcher enhance and promote the further study on soft topology to carry out a general framework for their applications in practical life.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Ahmad and A. Kharal. *On fuzzy soft sets*, Adv. Fuzzy Syst., (2009), Art. ID 586507, 1-6.
- [2] Ahu Acikgoz and Nihal Arabacioglu Tas, Some new soft sets and decompositions of some soft continuities, *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics*, 9(1)(2015), 23–35.
- [3] M. I. Ali, F. Feng, X. Liu, W. K. Min and M. Shabir. On some new operations in soft set theory, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 57(2009), 1547–1553.
- [4] H. Aktas and N. Cagman. Soft sets and soft groups, *Inform. Sci.*, 177(2007), 2726–2735.
- [5] S. Atmaca and I. Zorlutuna, On fuzzy soft topological spaces, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.*, 5(2013), 377–386.
- [6] Banu Pazar Varol and Halis Aygun. On soft Hausdorff spaces, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.*, 5(2013), 15–24.
- [7] N. Cagman, F. Citak and S. Enginoglu. Fuzzy parametrized fuzzy soft set theory and its applications, *Turkish Journal of Fuzzy Systems* 1(1)(2010), 21–35.
- [8] N. Cagman and S. Enginoglu. Soft set theory and uni-int decision making, *European J. Oper. Res.*, 207(2)(2010), 848–855.
- [9] S. Hussain and B. Ahmad. Some properties of soft topological spaces, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 62(2011), 4058–4067.
- [10] A. Kharal and B. Ahmad. Mappings of soft classes, *New Math. Nat. Comput.*, 7(3)(2011), 471–481.
- [11] D. V. Kovkov, V. M. Kolbanov and D. A. Molodtsov, Soft sets theory-based optimization, *Journal of Computer and Systems Sciences International*, 46(6)(2007), 872–880.
- [12] P. K. Maji, R. Biswas and A. R. Roy. Soft set theory, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 45(2003), 555–562.
- [13] P. K. Maji, R. Biswas and A. R. Roy. Fuzzy soft sets, *J. Fuzzy Math.*, 9(3)(2001), 589–602.
- [14] P. K. Maji, R. Biswas and A. R. Roy. Intuitionistic fuzzy soft sets, *J. Fuzzy Math.*, 9(3)(2001), 677–691.
- [15] P. Majumdar and S. K. Samanta. Generalised fuzzy soft sets, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 59(2010), 1425–1432.
- [16] W. K. Min. A note on soft topological spaces, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 62(2011), 3524–3528.
- [17] D. Molodtsov. Soft set theory-first results, *Comp. Math. Appl.*, 33(1999), 19–31.
- [18] D. Molodtsov, V. Y. Leonov and D. V. Kovkov. Soft sets technique and its application, *Nechetkie Sistemy i Myagkie Vychisleniya*, 1(1)(2006), 8–39.
- [19] A. Mukherjee and S. B. Chakraborty. On intuitionistic fuzzy soft relations, *Bull. Kerala Math. Assoc.*, 5(1)(2008), 35–42.
- [20] D. Pei and D. Miao, From soft sets to information systems, in: X. Hu, Q. Liu, A. Skowron, T. Y. Lin, R. R. Yager, B. Zhang (Eds.), *Proceedings of Granular Computing*, in: IEEE, 2(2005), 617–621.
- [21] E. Peyghan, B. Samadi and A. Tayebi. About soft topological spaces, *Journal of New Results in Science*, 2(2013), 60–75.
- [22] S. Roy and T. K. Samanta. A note on fuzzy soft topological spaces, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.*, 3(2)(2012), 305–311.
- [23] M. Shabir, and M. Naz. On soft topological spaces, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 61(2011), 1786–1789.
- [24] A. Vadivel and E. Elavarasan. Regular semiopen soft sets and maps in soft topological spaces, *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics*, 12(6)(2016), 877–891.
- [25] I. Zorlutuna, M. Akdag, W. K. Min and S. Atmaca. Remarks on soft topological spaces, *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics*, 3(2)(2012), 171–185.
- [26] Y. Zou and Z. Xiao. Data analysis approaches of soft sets under incomplete information, *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 21(2008), 941–945.

E. ELAVARASAN

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, SHREE RAGHAVENDRA ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE, KEEZHAMOONGLI-LADI, CHIDAMBARAM-608 102, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

Email address: maths.aras@gmail.com

A. VADIVEL

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, GOVT ARTS COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS), KARUR-639 005, TAMIL NADU,
INDIA

Email address: avmaths@gmail.com